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FORMATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL DERIVATIVES WITH PREFIXES

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Abstract: *This article talks about the formation of new derivatives of words that are part of phraseological combinations in French and Uzbek languages using prefixes.*

Key words: *lexical layer, derivational changes, prefixes, phraseological derivatives, phraseological units, affixation method.*

The changing nature of the language is a factor in the enrichment of the lexical layer, the creation of new words, and the discovery of new meanings. Derivative studies show that many language elements are borrowed from other languages, or a word is sometimes added to a root to form a new word, over time. Undergoes a semantic change and acquires new meanings. At the same time, such changes are also observed in contexts related to the communicative-emotional state. But studies show that mainly derivational changes are formed within the word, sometimes there is a change from a compound to a sentence. In this part, we will consider affix changes in words that are part of phraseological units.

The affix method of word formation has been thoroughly studied by linguists. Uzbek linguist Academician A. Ghulomov was the first to introduce the term word formation methods to Uzbek linguistics through his scientific works. After that, several scientists in their researches presented different types of word formation.

Today, the Uzbek language mainly distinguishes 3 ways of word formation: phonetic, affixation and composition. At this point, it should be said that Russian linguist N.M. Shansky, including abbreviation, distinguished four methods: lexical-semantic, morphological-semantic, lexical-syntactic and morphological.

In the French language, a unique classification has been made, including the above points. They are as follows:

1. Dérivation (affix method). This method is divided into such types as prefixation (préfixation), suffixation (dérivation suffixale), parasynthesis (dérivation parasynthétique);
2. Composition (composition method)
3. Conversion (conversion method). This method is also called dérivation improper in French.
4. Abbreviation (Abbreviation method). It is also divided into troncation (making words by shortening parts of the word) and siglaison (shortening of word combinations) methods.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that the method of affixation is recognized by different scientists in different languages. Let's consider how effective the affixation method is in the formation of new derivatives of phraseological units.

It is known that in the Uzbek language, the method of forming words by adding prefixes is less common than other methods. Prefixes are mainly characteristic of the Persian-Tajik language, and they are widely used to form words in the Uzbek language as well. Even today, new words are created from word-forming suffixes such as *be-*, *ser-*, *no-*, *ba-*. A unit-lexeme with an independent meaning in the modern Uzbek language can be the basis for creating several words that do not have a significant change in meaning. Similar word derivatives are also found in phraseological units. Lexical or phraseological derivatives, which appeared mainly in oral speech, later became popular, moved to fiction to show the communication environment. Or, on the contrary, a certain invention, which appeared due to scientific innovation, is also used in derivative speech, becomes "public property" and gives a new meaning (sometimes a figurative meaning). As an example, if we take the prefix *be-* used in the Uzbek language, it creates words such as *befarosat*, *betkaror*, *bebahra*, and becomes synonymous with the language suffix *-siz*. Today, new words are introduced using this prefix. Examples of religious customs are:

Stomach ache does not go away from sitting at the table "bebismillah", said Khoja, gritting his teeth.

(E. Malik. Shaytonvachchaning nayranglari. –T., "Sharq", 2013, 14 p)

In addition, a word that has a feature characteristic of a word-forming format, performs a function characteristic of an affix or an affixoid. For example, the "kam" component in words such as *kamgap*, *kamkatnov*, *kamharajat* has such a feature.

In French, one of the methods of word formation is la dérivation, which is formed by adding affixes and non-independent words from new lexical units. Word formation with prefixes is common in French. According to the form of formation, there are such types as la dérivation parasynthétique (that is, formed with both an affix and a suffix) and la dérivation régressive (in which a suffix is shortened). At the same time, in the linguistics of the French language, the type of derivation improper is also distinguished, in which the word changes grammatically in nature. For example, the indefinite form of the verb *rire* takes the article and becomes a noun: *un rire éclatant*. In this place, there is no change in the form of the word, and there is no strong semantic change in the meaning of the word. In particular, some components of the phraseological units we are studying are formed by the parasynthetic derivation method.

Prefixes borrowed from Latin and other languages are widely used in French, and even today new words are formed through them: *a-*, *an-*, *dé-*, *in-*, *im-*, *irr-*, *re-*, *co-* *anti* Prefixes such as *-*, *aéro-*, *auto-*, *mal-*, *ex-*, *para-*, *hyper-*, *hypo-*, *syn-*, *dys-* can easily replace prepositions and sometimes independent words. If new derivatives are made from verbs that have a phraseological meaning with these prefixes, semantically close verbs are formed. For example, if we take the verb *atterrir* formed with the prefix *a-*, this verb is formed by adding the prefix *a-* to the noun *terre* *-er* (soil) and the suffix forming the indefinite form of the verbs of the second group *-ir*. What is noteworthy is the change of meaning of this verb depending on the change of time and the development of science and technology: in the past centuries, *atterer* (to touch the ground, touch the ground) was formed as a verb of the first group. From it *arriver finalement* (to finally arrive) is also used in the figurative sense:

Après deux heures de marche, nous avons atterri dans une petite auberge.

(M. Pagnol. Le secret du masque de fer. Paris, 1973, 75-p)

So, it can be seen from the above examples that the process of forming new words with affixes in languages of different systems is continuous. The Uzbek language has little change compared to the French language. But in French, it is possible to create several new lexical units from different affixes, and sometimes from one affix. Although the main meaning of the core of this unit becomes dominant even when derivatives are added, it acquires different phraseological meanings under the original meaning when it is transferred to the speech process and communication.

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